

THE ROLE OF EFFECTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: Foreign language teaching methods are comparative, mixed and correct methods. From the point of view of the grammar-translation type of the method, the foreign language is studied for general educational purposes. Different grammar exercises are taught in order to develop the logical potential of the language learner. The systematic grammatical theory of foreign language teaching through the above method is of primary importance.

Key words: grammatical form, means of communication, method, foreign language, text, translation.

Introduction:

One of the important things in human society is language learning. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired practically in the family, that is, in the natural environment, among the public, or in a gathering, that is, in classes. Theoretically studied knowledge is knowledge related to language phenomena. Learning foreign languages, especially multilingualism, more precisely, polyglossia, is important in the era of growing international relations.

Currently, many students and pupils are studying three different languages. In the theory of education, they are referred to by their own names. They are: mother tongue, second foreign language and foreign language.

We know that everyone's native language is the first language that plays a key role in the development of mental thinking. Certain concepts learned through words in the mother tongue are manifested in the sound and written appearance of words in a foreign language in the process of mastering a second or foreign language. The mother tongue, the second foreign language and the word learned in a foreign language (*for example: tree-tree-un arbre-ein Baum*) are three in terms of number, but the concept understood from the expression of meaning is the same: "Some meaning" Noda is the most important type of plant for all humanity and nature, for existence in general. Readers and students logically connect the concepts they learn in a foreign language with words in their native language.

When thinking about the second language, it is considered as the language of the fraternal nations, the language of the neighbors. It's no secret that language is an invaluable tool that helps to maintain good relations with the surrounding society, gain respect, make friends, and leave a good name in the life of a person. The term second language is a familiar concept for students studying in other languages in secondary and higher educational institutions.

A foreign language is the language of a foreign country. Western European languages (*French, German, Spanish, English*) and languages from Eastern countries (*Turkish, Arabic, Urdu, Persian, Japanese, Chinese*) are taught in our republic, and these languages occupy a place in the curriculum of the educational plan.

The process of teaching all three languages is different: in the first place, thinking in one's own language is developed, in addition, the understanding and feeling of features specific to phonetics, lexis and grammar are related to learning other languages. is liquid; secondly, the procedure of language learning begins with one's mother tongue, then moves to a second

language and then to a foreign language; thirdly, mother tongue and second language are learned in a natural situation, and a foreign language is learned in an artificial environment. From the above concept, it is clear that teaching and learning a foreign language among the three languages is significantly different in some specific aspects. This situation, in its place, causes the use of appropriate foreign language teaching methods and technologies.

Basically, the methods of teaching a foreign language are known by four names and at the same time they are popular. They are: direct, mixed and comparative and translation methods.

For example, the translation method: they are mainly of two types, grammar-translation and text-translation methods.

From the theory of the grammar-translation method, foreign languages are mastered for general educational purposes. Various grammar exercises are performed in order to form the mental and logical thinking of the language learner. In the context of teaching a foreign language through the grammar-translation method, systematic grammar theory is of primary importance.

The main tasks of the method are as follows:

Language teaching is based on written speech.

Grammar was taken as the subject of study, and the lexicon was chosen accordingly. Grammatical exercises were the main method of work.

Grammatical rules are memorized and it is recommended to make a sentence based on the rules.

Grammatical forms and the meaning of words are revealed in the means of word-for-word translation.

The language material was mastered by means of word-for-word translation and memorization.

Limited to individual memorization of words out of context.

The main function of the text-translation method is also directed to general education, but the goal is not to develop logical thinking, as in the grammar-translation method, but to the development of the general mental potential of the language learner.

1. A foreign language is taught based on written speech.
2. The link and often the original text is taken.
3. A lot of effort and time was spent on analysis when studying the text.
4. The method of clarifying the meaning of words and grammatical forms - translation.
5. The language material is learned through translation and memorization.

Method without translation. This method is divided into two types: natural and correct methods.

For example, one of the main tasks of the natural method is that learning a foreign language should be compatible with the conditions of mastering the mother tongue. Another goal of the method is to learn to speak a foreign language and, at the same time, to learn to speak about everyday life topics. In this regard, we can cite the creative activities of method exponents as a clear example.

Method of M. Berliz. He is a famous Methodist scientist in the history of foreign language teaching methodology who organized foreign language teaching courses in the USA in 1878 and created textbooks.

The main methodological views of M. Berlís's system can be read from the preface of the textbooks written by him:

Perception of language material should be immanent, without translation. Direct connection between words and objects, lack of connection with the words of the native language, and understanding of grammatical concepts in the context, without the participation of the mind, without comparison with the native language.

Strengthening language material by imitating the teacher.

Non-participation of the mother tongue in learning a foreign language.

Clarifying the meaning of language phenomena with the help of exhibitions.

Oral presentation of new material first.

A pair of teacher and student speech (conversation) encouraging students to engage in speech activity is a preferred way of working.

F. Guen's method. French Methodist F. Guen was one of the representatives of the natural method, and he was an advocate of learning a foreign language in practice as if he were learning his mother tongue. He was the first to discover the classification of the lexicon by topics (life at home, school, society, nature) in methodology.

He implemented the study of a foreign language based on the following rules:

1. A person learns a language based on his needs.
2. Selection of sentence rather than word as teaching unit.
3. Oral speech is considered primary in language teaching.

Based on his research, F. Guen divides the vocabulary of a foreign language into three main types: words denoting objective, subjective and expressive concepts. An example of the objective group is words related to the world and nature, such as life, society. Examples of the subjective group are words that express concepts related to the human spirit: to understand, to want, to laugh, and the third category includes concepts that combine objective and subjective words: beauty, friendship, etc.

Mixed methods. As the teaching of foreign languages continues to increase, due to the lack of the expected results from inexperienced (natural and correct) methods in public schools, it is necessary to switch from the previously used methods to omukhta, i.e. hybrid lessons (language teaching).) was created.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it is worth mentioning that learning foreign languages is a multifaceted research, and in this process, a person becomes even more perfect. For example, experiencing psychological changes, including the process of comparing the mother tongue and a foreign language. Of course, it is necessary to use different teaching methods in this process. Instead, using different methods will give results as expected and provide intensity in learning a foreign language. This simplifies the process of language learning and gives sufficient results as expected. That is, it opens the door to many conveniences and opportunities for learning and teaching a foreign language. Through this, the intended goal will be achieved more easily, and the above methods will definitely make a significant contribution to it. From this we can understand that the use of methods in teaching and learning a foreign language is quite important.

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